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● Notes on *Eterusia raja* Moore, [1858] (Lepidoptera, Zygaenidae, Chalcosiinae) from China

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Abstract: Living individuals of *Eterusia raja* Moore, [1858] are recorded for the first time in China (southern Xizang and northwestern Yunnan). An updated synthesis of its morphology, distribution, altitudinal range, flight period, and flower-visiting behavior on *Viburnum cylindricum* Buch.-Ham. ex D. Don is provided. In addition, its putative host plant is discussed, the nomenclatural date is emended, and Chinese common names of the *raja* group species are proposed.

Keywords: China, new record, taxonomy, Xizang, Yunnan, Zygaenidae

● 王柄脉锦斑蛾 *Eterusia raja* Moore, [1858] 在中国的记述 (鳞翅目, 斑蛾科, 锦斑蛾亚科)

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摘要: 本文首次在中国 (西藏南部、云南西北部) 记录到王柄脉锦斑蛾 *Eterusia raja* Moore, [1858] 的活体, 完善了对该种形态、分布、海拔、飞行期及访花水红木 *Viburnum cylindricum* Buch.-Ham. ex D. Don 生态行为的认识。同时, 讨论了其可能的寄主植物, 更正了命名年份, 并提出了 *raja* 种组物种的中文名。

关键词: 中国, 新纪录, 分类学, 西藏, 云南, 斑蛾科

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● Introduction

The genus *Eterusia* Hope, 1841 is a distinctive monophyletic group of chalcosiine moths (Lepidoptera: Zygaenidae: Chalcosiinae) distributed from the Indian subcontinent through mainland Southeast Asia to East Asia (Yen 2003a; Yen *et al.* 2005a, b). Adults are typically day-flying and well known for their complex sexual dimorphism, polymorphism and mimetic wing patterns, often exhibiting a spotted or banded forewing and a polychrome hindwing bearing a large central patch and several smaller spots of various shapes and colors (Yen 2003b; Huang *et al.* 2023).

The *raja* species-group was recently characterized by Huang *et al.* (2023) based on external morphology and genitalia characters. This group includes *E. raja* Moore, [1858] and *E. sinoraja* Huang & Horie, 2023. It is diagnosed by the metallic bluish dorsal abdomen, forewing with yellowish band or spots, hindwing with vivid orange pattern, and male genitalia characterized by a broad and trapezoidal modified 8th tergite, elongated posterior arms of the 8th sternite with dentations, and a strongly S-shaped aedeagus.

E. raja was regarded by Jordan (1908) as “one of the most beautiful species of the Zygaenids”. It has previously been known from northeastern India and southern Xizang (Sondhi *et al.* 2021). During the Wild Fun Insect Enthusiasts Society [野趣虫友会] 2025 entomological expedition to Motuo, Xizang, living individuals of this species were collected for the first time in China. A new provincial record is also reported from northwestern Yunnan. Based on specimens and literature, the morphology, distribution, altitudinal range, flight period, and flower-visiting behavior of *E. raja* are summarized. In addition, its putative host plant is discussed, the nomenclatural date is emended, and the Chinese common names of *E. raja* group species are formally proposed.

● Material and methods

Specimens examined are deposited in the following institutional and private collections: Shanghai Pudong Youth & Children’s Center (SPYCC), Shanghai, China; the private collection of Zhuo-heng Jiang (CJZH), Kunming, China; the private collections of Shuai Zhao (CZS), Tianjin, China. Abdomen was removed and macerated in hot 10% KOH solution for examination of male genitalia, and the extracted structures were stored in a microvial filled with pure glycerol.

Adult habitus photographs were taken with an OM System OM-1 Mark II camera fitted with an OM System M.Zuiko Digital ED 90mm F3.5 Macro IS PRO lens. Genitalia photographs were taken with the same camera and lens combination, extended with an OM System M.Zuiko Digital 2x teleconverter MC-20. All images above were captured as focal series and focus-stacked using Helicon Focus 8.3. Flower-visiting photograph was taken with a Canon EOS R7 camera fitted with a Canon RF 100–400 mm F5.6–8 IS USM lens. The distribution map was generated using Google Earth Pro. Final image processing and plate assembly were completed in Adobe Photoshop 2026. Terminology of adult and genitalia morphology follows Klots (1970) and Yen *et al.* (2005a).

● Taxonomy

Genus *Eterusia* Hope, 1841

Eterusia Hope, 1841, *Trans. Linn. Soc.* 18: 445.

Type species: *Eterusia tricolor* Hope, 1841.

The *Eterusia raja* species-group

***Eterusia sinoraja* Huang & Horie, 2023 华王柄脉锦斑蛾**

Figs 4–5

Eterusia sinoraja Huang *et al.*, 2023, *Zootaxa* 5270 (1): 125, figs 1–3, 10, 13, 16, 18.**Type locality:** Yingjing County, Ya'an City, Sichuan Province, China.**Material examined:** 1♂ (CJZH), CHINA: Sichuan Province, Ya'an City, Yingjing County, Anjing Township, Yinchanggou Mine [银厂沟矿山]; alt. 1900 m, VIII.2025, leg. local collector; 1♀ (CZS), same collecting locality, VIII.2024, leg. local collector.**Distribution.** China (Sichuan).***Eterusia raja* Moore, [1858] 王柄脉锦斑蛾**

Figs 1–3, 6–10

Eterusia raja Moore, [1858], in Horsfield & Moore, *A catalogue of the lepidopterous insects in the Museum of Natural History at the East-India House* 2: 320, pl. 8a, fig. 2; Walker, 1864: 117; Kirby, 1892: 49; Fletcher, 1925: 5; Endo & Kishida, 1999: 99; Yen *et al.*, 2005a: 294, 2005b: 361; Sondhi *et al.*, 2021: 4, image 10; Huang *et al.*, 2023: 129.*Eterusia rajah* Jordan, 1908, in Seitz A (Ed), *Die Gross-Schmetterlinge der Erde* 10: 33, pl. 6, line d.*Heterusia raja* Hampson, 1892, *The Fauna of British India (Moths)* 1: 259; Dudgeon, 1899: 298.*Heterusia rajah* Hering, 1922, *Archiv f. Naturg.* 88 A (11): 63.**Type locality:** Darjeeling, West Bengal State, India.**Material examined:** 1♂, (SPYCC), CHINA: Xizang Autonomous Region, Linzhi City, Motuo County, Gelin Village, Piaomiao Tea Garden [缥缈茶园]; 29°12'25"N, 95°10'32"E; alt. 1759 m, 20.VIII.2025, leg. Xin-yao Lu, SPYCC003; 1♂, (SPYCC), same collecting locality and date, leg. Jin Zhai, SPYCC004; 1♀, (CJZH), same collecting locality and date, leg. Jin Zhai; 1♂, (CJZH), CHINA: Yunnan Province, Fugong County, Shiyueliang [石月亮]; alt. 1830 m, 21.VII.2025, leg. Xin Wang.**Diagnosis** (Figs 1–3, 8–9). Head—Antenna metallic blue, bipectinate with black rami. Vertex metallic green. Frontoclypeus prominent. Thorax—Dorsally metallic green. Ventrally yellow. Collar narrowly crimson. Forewing—Elongated and narrow. Ground color metallic deep green. A transverse band composed of 6 yellow spots extends from middle of costa to tornus, the band edged with black on both sides and the veins within it blue. A narrow, diffuse pale green band presents beyond the discal cell. Cilia black. Hindwing—Ground color orange, with veins broadly bordered black. A curved black submarginal band extending from upper angle of discal cell to outer margin at vein Cu₂. Outer margin black. Abdominal margin broadly blue-green. Cilia black. Abdomen—Dorsally metallic green. Ventrally yellow. 8th tergite medially trapezoid, with a pair of apodeme anteriorly and posteriorly. 8th sternite comprises a dumbbell-like anterior section and a pair of blade-like posterior arms bearing dentation along the inner side. Medial section of anterior sclerite 1/4 the width of remainder.

Male genitalia (Figs 6–7)—Uncus-tegumen complex comprising rounded lateral lobes and a triangular medial section; tegumenal arms slender, fused with vinculum; anterior tegumenal apodeme moderately sclerotized, broad at base and abruptly narrowed distally, then bent downwards. Valva moderately sclerotized; cucullus nearly uniform in width; distal end of inner projection of Saccus narrower and rounded. Saccus rounded. Aedeagus strongly S-shaped, medio-ventrally narrowed and with a protuberance, apex tapering.

Distribution. China (Yunnan, Xizang), India (Assam, Nagaland, West Bengal).**Bionomics.** Adults fly from June to September, at altitudes between approximately 1500 and 1830 m. In Motuo, over 20 individuals were observed flying actively and visiting flowers of *Viburnum cylindricum* Buch.-Ham. ex D. Don (Adoxaceae) between 13:30 and 14:00 local time, at an approximate height of 5–6 m in the canopy (Fig. 10).

FIGURES 1–5. Adults of *Eterusia raja* species-group: 1 *E. raja*, male, Xizang, China, SPYCC003 (SPYCC) 2 *ditto*, male, Xizang, China, SPYCC004 (SPYCC) 3 *ditto*, female, Xizang, China (CJZH) 4 *E. sinoraja*, male, Sichuan, China (CJZH) 5 *ditto*, female, Sichuan, China (CZS). A = upperside B = underside. Scale bar = 2.0 cm. Photo: Chen-yu Gu (1–2); Zhuo-heng Jiang (3–5).

FIGURES 6–9. Male terminalia of *E. raja* (Xizang, China, SYPCC003): 6 genital capsule 7 aedeagus 8 Sternite 9 tergite. Scale bar = 2.0 mm. Photo: Jian-qiu Kang.

Remarks. *E. raja* is externally similar to *E. sinoraja*, but can be distinguished by the following characters: 1) the forewing bears a compact transverse band composed of yellowish spots in the medial area, whereas *E. sinoraja* has two loose rows that occupy both the medial and postmedial areas; 2) the hindwing is broadly blue-green at vannal region, whereas in *E. sinoraja* only the veins and outer margin at the anal angle are blue-green, the remainder being orange with black veins; 3) in male genitalia, the distal end of the inner projection of the sacculus is narrower and rounded, in contrast to the broader and flat distal end in *E. sinoraja*; the cucullus is nearly uniform in width along its entire length, while in *E. sinoraja* it is basally narrowed and gradually expanded distally; the aedeagus is medio-ventrally narrower near the protuberance, and the protuberance is longer; the medial section of the anterior sclerite of the 8th sternite is narrower; 4) in female genitalia, the antrum is smaller and the ostium bursae is slightly narrower (Huang *et al.* 2023).

● Discussion

Nomenclatural year. The publication date of *E. raja* has long been cited as 1859. Examination of the original volume shows that cover bears the imprint date “1858–9”, but the part in which Moore described the species was actually issued on 30 June 1858, as recorded at the foot of page 334. In accordance with the Article 21.6 of *International Code of Zoological Nomenclature* (ICZN, 1999), the earliest demonstrable date of issue takes precedence for nomenclatural purposes. Therefore, the nomenclatural authorship of *E. raja* is cited herein as Moore, [1858], rather than Moore, 1859.

FIGURE 10. Adults of *E. raja* visiting flowers of *V. cylindricum* at Piaomiao Tea Garden, Gelin Village, Motuo County, Linzhi City, Xizang, China, 1759 m, 20.VIII.2025. Photo: Xin-yao Lu.

FIGURE 11. Distribution of the *Eterusia raja* species-group: *E. raja* (red square) and *E. sinoraja* (yellow triangle).

Distribution. *E. raja* was previously considered endemic to northeastern India and southern Xizang. Historical records attributed to Sikkim (Hampson 1887; Kirby 1892) lack precise localities, and the “Tukvar, Sikkim” record of Dudgeon (1899) is in fact referable to the Tukvar Valley in the Darjeeling District, West Bengal, rather than the present-day state of Sikkim. Other verified Indian records are from the Naga Hills, Assam (Jordan 1908; Huang *et al.* 2023) and Khuzama, Kohima District, Nagaland (Sondhi *et al.* 2026). In China, the species is formally recorded for the first time based on living individuals from Motuo, Xizang and Fugong, Yunnan. Prior to this, the only record from China was a hindwing of a dead individual reported by Sondhi *et al.* (2021) from southern Xizang (Cuona City, Xizang). An insect enthusiast also mentioned through personal communication the occurrence of *E. raja* from the Dulongjiang Township, Gongshan Dulong and Nu Autonomous County, Nujiang Lisu Autonomous Prefecture, Yunnan Province, near the Myanmar border, with the earliest records of adults flying from June to July, further extending its known range eastward. Taken together, these records indicate that *E. raja* is distributed along the southern slopes of the eastern Himalayas, extending from northeastern India into southwestern China, and probably also into Bhutan and northern Myanmar.

Biology. *V. cylindricum* is documented here for the first time as a nectar source for *E. raja*. This evergreen tree is common in montane forests of the eastern Himalayas and southern China, flowering from June to October (Hsu, 1988), which coincides well with the records of *E. raja*. The host plant and immature stages of *E. raja* remain unknown. Notably, the Chinese collecting site and the type locality are both surrounded by extensive tea plantations. Since several congeneric species are known to feed on the leaves of *Camellia sinensis* (L.) Kuntze (Theaceae), e.g. *E. aedea* (Linnaeus, 1763) and *E. risa* (Doubleday, 1844) (Mitra *et al.* 2018), it is plausible that *E. raja* also feeds on tea plants. Field surveys are required to clarify its exact host range.

Chinese common names. The generic Chinese name “柄脉锦斑蛾” combines “锦斑蛾”, the standard vernacular for chalcosiine moths, with “柄脉” (petiole and veins), referring to the characteristic larval feeding damage that reduces leaves to petioles and main veins. The specific epithet *raja*, from the Sanskrit *rājan* (राजन्, “king”), alludes to the species’ majestic appearance and is rendered as “王” in the Chinese name. The name *sinoraja* combines the Latin prefix *sino-* (Chinese) with *raja*, indicating a Chinese ally of *E. raja*. “华” corresponds to *sino-* and “王” to *raja*. Accordingly, the Chinese common names “王柄脉锦斑蛾” (*E. raja*) and “华王柄脉锦斑蛾” (*E. sinoraja*) are formally proposed here.

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● Additional information

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Photo Gallery

梔子花多翼蛾 *Alucita flavofascia* (Inoue, 1958)

Sunqiao, Pudong New Area, Shanghai

photograph by Ning ZHANG [张宁]